

ARTICLE TEMPLATE

Safeguarding European space sovereignty - Recommendations for Operational Climate Services

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ABSTRACT

European space sovereignty and European security require operational climate services. Operational climate services would include both the regular production of high-resolution climate projections, similar to operational weather forecasts, as well as the derivation of space-sector-specific climate impact indices. Climate projections are mainly executed within the scientific realm, while climate indices are often-times developed in short-lived projects, leaving climate risk assessments of critical European Space segments, including the Guiana Space Center in Kourou, French Guiana, reliant on the foresight of climate scientists. The absence of comprehensive and periodic climate risk assessments for different areas of operation at the Guiana Space Center could compromise Europe's capability to launch and replenish its earth observation, navigation, and telecommunication satellites in the event of damage or destruction. The consequences can be significant, with potential impacts on European security, defense, and economic stability. In this paper we advocate for increased collaboration between climate service scientists and strategic operational managers of European security and space infrastructure to ensure relevant and usable climate indices be developed through the co-design process. Ultimately, climate-related hazards should be considered a space threat by the European Union.

KEYWORDS

European Space Agency; European Defence Agency; European Security; Climate Risk; CORDEX-CORE; Critical Infrastructure Resilience; Strategic Planning; Natech; SEVESO III

1. Introduction

Over the last several decades, Europe has focused its investments in three space sectors: (i) Global Navigation Space Systems (GNSS), (ii) Earth Observation, and (iii) Telecommunications (3, 90, 101). All three sectors play an essential role in the daily lives of European citizens, as well as European Security and Defense. Given the importance of these sectors, it is essential that European space sovereignty be safeguarded. More specifically, European space sovereignty hinges on its ability to launch satellites into different orbits. The primary European launch site for Low-Earth-Orbit and Geo-stationary-Orbit is the Guiana Space Center in Kourou, French Guiana. French Guiana is a region of France and is one of the outermost regions of the European Union. This unique site offers launches using Vega, Soyuz, and Ariane vehicles, allowing it to meet a variety of European space access needs. As such, the Guiana Space Center is a critical component of the European security and defense infrastructure. It is needed for the replenishment of constellations, replacement of individual satellites, and the deployment of future constellations (90). The Guiana Space Center also plays a significant role in the European economy. The space economy is a "vertical" economic

enabler of several industries, including the manufacturing and servicing of launch vehicles, satellites, and ground equipment. The space industry attracted over EUR 14.8 billion of investments since the year 2000 (3). The Guiana Space Center is built, operated, and maintained by Arianespace (France) and the European Space Agency (ESA, Europe), and simultaneously boosts the European economy, while limiting the need for foreign reliance on access to space. It also ensures European personnel develop the technical capabilities to address European needs in various space sectors. Given the importance of the Guiana Space Center, as a potential single point of failure for European autonomous access to space, including the European security sector, it is prudent to ensure this site regularly undertakes a climate risk and vulnerability assessment. In this work, we demonstrate why operational climate services, which includes providing simulations of climate projections and the derivation of space-sector specific indices, are essential for safeguarding Europe's autonomous access to space.

1.1. *European Security and Defence - A reliance on Space*

European security relies on earth observations, secure communication, and the ability to navigate. The European Union Satellite Centre, together with the Copernicus Security Service, for example, provide geo-spatial intelligence to the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX), European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA), and European Union External and Security Actions (SESA). Without these technologies, not only is the broad European security environment at risk, so is its defence capabilities including force readiness and military operations (1). The European Defense Agency's 2023 Report on the 'Impacts of climate change on defence-related critical energy infrastructure' (9) identified the need for guidelines to help assess climate risk in the defence sector. Furthermore, the World Security Report (2020) (1) recommended the integration of climate knowledge into the risk assessment, early warning, surveillance, and operational preparations in order to climate-proof military infrastructure, including the adoption of adaptation measures. Tavares da Costa et al. (10) recently produced a climate risk management guide to support the incorporation of climate change considerations into plans and budgets of defence programs. This should also include the space domain.

The space domain, as defined in the European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence, includes all elements relevant to the functioning of space systems and the delivery of space-based services within the European Union (EU) and its Member States (90). Roughly speaking, the space system can be broken into three components: (i) the space segment; (ii) the ground and launch segment; and (iii) the link segment (including air space and terminals). Climate related-hazards have the potential to disrupt both the ground and link segments (8, 100). Climate related-hazards and the risks they pose are derived from climate projections (See Section 3). In French Guiana, the climate projections available are performed sporadically by scientists and are not "operational", by which we mean performed on a regular basis in a standardized manner as is the case of weather forecasts. Consequently, the climate data available to assess the readiness and resilience of the Guiana Space Center to climate change is ad hoc. We elaborate upon this in Section 3.

Traditionally, risks arising from natural hazards have been considered as a "safety" and not "security" concern. Safety management commonly refers to measures, both preventative and reactive, aimed to minimize accidental or unintentional harm to people, operational assets and activities, data/information, as well as reputation (28,

42, 41). Security management commonly refers to the measures aimed to prevent intentional harm to people, operational assets and activities, data/information, and reputation by unlawful actors (28, 42, 41). Importantly, space security management also includes the ability to maintain international peace and security (99). As such, in this paper, we argue that climate-related hazards should be considered within both space safety and space security discussions, in a similar manner as space debris (99). The silo-ed approach of pigeonholing climate-related hazards as only a 'safety risk' has, as we will show in Sections 2 and 4, lead to a false sense of security which can lead to an important security risk, threatening European space autonomy.

2. Guiana Space Center, Kourou, French Guiana

2.1. *A brief history*

The Guiana Space Center (GSC) was created in 1964 after the independence of Algeria forced France to abandon the Hammaguir space base (39). The city of Kourou was an attractive place to develop a launch site due to its proximity to the equator and the sea. Launches near the equator, in particular eastward launches, take maximum advantage of the Earth's rotation, reducing the amount of fuel and time needed to reach space. Launches over the sea also reduce risk to urban areas and human life as boosters fall. French Guiana also had the added advantages of low chances of tropical cyclones, low risk of earthquakes, and low population density (39, 38).

2.2. *The geological environment*

Figure 1. Kourou city and surrounding area in 1950 (left) and 2018 (right). Source: Institut national de l'information géographique et forestière (IGN), Photothèque Nationale Republique Francaise. Accessed: 16.01.2024. <https://remonterletemps.ign.fr/comparer/>

The historical city of Kourou was built on clay soil and lays further inland of the mouth of the Kourou river relative to the modern day boundaries of the city (38, 103) (Fig. 1, Fig. 2). Comparably, the vast majority of the modern city of Kourou, which the French built to house the employees of the GSC, has been built on sand formed in the Demerara (2) as can be seen in the lithological map, "Feuille 1192", of the "Inventory and atlas of raw material reserves for the construction sector in French Guiana - Final report" of the french geological survey, Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières (BRGM) (2) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Lithographic map (scale 1/100000) around the city of Kourou (Feuille 1192). Source and Copyright: Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières, (BRGM 2022). Permission from BRGM to reproduce these images pending. Accessed: 16.01.2024. https://www.brgm.fr/sites/default/files/styles/background_centered_full_width_desktop/public/images/2022-09/reference-reserves-materiaux-btp-guyane-002.jpg?h=6393905a

2.3. Local Narratives

Herein lies an additional complication which stems from the colonial mindset France took when developing the modern city of Kourou. The indigenous people of French Guiana considered this newly developed area of land as "belong(ing) to the sea" (38). They were accustomed to the highly dynamic nature of the coastline, where migrating mud banks and cheniers (sandy beaches over mud), combined with strong tides and high energy waves, periodically caused intense periods of erosion resulting in the coastline retreating by tens of meters in a few months or even several kilometers in a few years (81, 80, 38). The closest point of the GSC, the Ariane launch pad, is approximately 2 km from the coast (103). Mangroves provided natural protection of the area from coastal erosion, however, in the 1990s French Foreign Legion were order to remove the mangroves in order to improve the view from villas in the city (38). The city of Kourou now faces chronic flooding and coastal erosion, which will be compounded with rising sea levels (40, 5).

2.4. Changing environment

Kourou's geographical position presents a paradox. Its proximity to the sea and equator, while making it an attractive location for launching rockets, also exposes it to certain vulnerabilities. The tropical, coastal location leaves it susceptible to the impacts of climate change, including rising sea levels, coastal floods, coastal erosion, and

(a) Launch infrastructure at the Guiana Space Center, Kourou, French Guiana. Source: Pline (2009).
 (b) Land projected to be below 10-year flood level in 2100. Source and copyright: Climate Central (2024).

Figure 3. (a) Map of the infrastructure for the Ariane and Vega launchers at the Europe's Spaceport the Guiana Space Center, Kourou, French Guiana. Source: Pline (2009). License: CC BY-SA 3.0. Accessed: 06.01.2024. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Plan_Centre_Spatial_Guyanais-en.svg (b) Land projected to be below 10-year flood level in 2100. Settings applied: SSP5-8.5 scenario, IPCC(2021) Leading consensus, Excluded areas isolated by higher land. Additional settings and description found in link. Source and copyright: Climate Central (2024). Accessed: 06.01.2024. https://coastal.climatecentral.org/map/15/-52.7127/5.2254/?theme=sea_level_rise&map_type=year&basemap=roadmap&contiguous=true&elevation_model=best_available&forecast_year=2100&pathway=ssp5rcp85&percentile=p50&refresh=true&return_level=return_level_10&r1_model=gtsr&slr_model=ipcc_2021_med Terms of Use: https://www.climatecentral.org/what-we-do/legal#content_licensing.

increasing temperatures.

Climate projections add another layer of complexity to this issue. The Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (18) presents a sobering picture. Under the SSP5-8.5 scenario, it predicts that by 2100, the area currently below the 10-year flood level will expand significantly (Fig. 3).

The impacts of climate change also extends beyond the Guiana Space Center to the city of Kourou. The environmental changes affecting in Kourou will directly impact the health and safety of most, if not all, personnel working at the Guiana Space Center. Incorporating the knowledge and experience collected by the Observatoire de la Dynamique Côtière de Guyane (110) regarding all French Guyanese coastal phenomena will be essential.

Adaptation to climate change in French Guiana will need to incorporate local knowledge in adaptation measures as it already faces an uphill battle due to its remote location, weaker infrastructure, and limited economic activities (5, 4). Examples of applying local narratives in climate risk governance can be found in Krauss and Bremer (69) and (70).

2.5. Natch Risks due to climate change

As an overseas department of France, French Guiana is subject to EU legislation and agreements, such as the Critical Entities Resilience Directive (2022/2557) (94) and the SEVESO III Directive (91) which provides a framework for risk management measures to prevent major accidents involving dangerous substances and to limit their consequences. The Guiana Space Center, with its launch facilities and fuel production plant, is classified as a SEVESO III entity. In fact, there are 16 SEVESO "haut" entities in French Guiana as of 2022 (102).

SEVESO III and critical infrastructure entities, have a great deal of experience in addressing natural hazards in their risk assessments. Such assessments are based on historical events. The natural hazards considered include e.g. floods, earthquakes, strong winds, waves (11, 12, 45). While these assessment address a range of hazard probabilities and intensities, they neither address changes in frequency, duration, and intensity of the hazards under climate change, nor does it address an overall changing environment - including degrading soil, prolonged exposure to heat stress, sea-level rise, and coastal erosion. A traditional hazard-by-hazard risk assessments also does not capture compounding or systemic risk. Consider, for example, a storm near or on the coast with a return period of >100-years. Heavy precipitation, as well as storm surges, could lead to flooding and amplify coastal erosion, which may destabilize a facility's stability which in turn is subjected to stronger than normal wind conditions. Thus, climate change risks are not sufficiently addressed within the existing SEVESO III Directive. Ultimately the risk of Natural Hazards Triggering Technological (Natech) events, where natural hazards trigger major accidents involving fires, explosions, or toxic releases of dangerous substances is underestimated when climate change is not accounted for (13).

Ultimately, *climate risk management*, which must be distinguished from *disaster risk management*, includes a climate risk assessment component. Climate risk assessments include the evaluation of hazards, exposure, vulnerability, using climate projections of the future (15, 14). Climate projections, encompass different plausible scenarios of greenhouse gas emissions and atmospheric concentrations, aerosol concentrations, and land-use change (44, 43). In a climate risk assessment of threats to assets, infrastructure, and ecosystems in French Guiana, the European Environment Agency Climate Risk Assessment Full Report (5) considered sea level rise and tropical cyclones. The report does not include coastal erosion, although it does emphasize this aspect requires further investigation. It is unclear whether the strategic importance of the Guiana Space Center or the SEVESO III sites was accounted for in the report as there was no mention of them.

3. Climate Services for Space Security

Ensuring climate projections are available for the derivation of climate hazards over critical infrastructure entities, such as the GSC, is crucial for conducting effective climate risk assessments. Without a comprehensive climate risk assessment, one can not reduce risk or develop resilience. This is vital for the infrastructure's long-term sustainability and operational efficiency.

At present, if one wanted to perform a systematic climate risk assessment for the GSC on a semi-regular basis, they would run into two hurdles. First, the simulations of climate projections are not operationalized, meaning performed on a regular basis following a standardized practice. This implies their production can be erratic, and consequently, our understanding of projected climate hazards. We elaborate upon this in Section 3.1. Second, climate model output is oftentimes not immediately usable by managers or decision makers of day-to-day functions of critical infrastructure (79). Significant efforts are required to customize and extract localized climate information relevant and useful for decision making. We elaborate on this in Section 3.2 while advocating the need for operationalized climate services to help co-develop indicators which can be used in climate risk assessments.

3.1. *Climate projections*

Climate risk assessments are comprised of three components: hazards, exposure, and vulnerability. Climate hazards, and their projected changes in terms of intensity, duration, and frequency are often derived from climate model simulations. Currently, climate model projections lay within the purview of the scientific community. The production of climate projections are coordinated internationally on a voluntary basis (29) and usually within short-term projects. This includes the simulations comprising the 5th and 6th phases of the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project (CMIP5 and CMIP6) experiments (26, 27) for global climate models, as well as the Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiments (CORDEX-CORE, EURO-CORDEX) (46, 48) for regional (continental scale) simulations, which are both widely used.

The French geological survey (BRGM) published a dedicated climate report for French Guiana in 2022 (7). This report provides a list of projected climate hazards including a significant decrease in rainfall, an intensification of hot days and nights, stronger winds, increasing sea level rise, chronic submersion, and changes in wave energy (7). These projections are based on global circulation model simulations from the CMIP5 and CMIP6, as well as an ensemble of simulations, made by Chauvin et al. (50) in the context of the Changement Climatique et Conséquences sur les Antilles Françaises (C3AF) project (109), using the ARPEGE atmospheric global climate model (GCM) (7).

Both the BRGM (7) and European Environment Agency (EEA) (5) studies cover the whole of French Guiana. For a localized climate risk assessment of the Guiana Space Center, it would best to use projections with the highest spatial resolution. Higher spatial resolution is particularly important for regions with sharp topographic gradients or land-sea contrast in order to resolve observed features of the atmospheric kinetic energy spectrum. This is commonly referred to as the effective resolution, which is important for representing atmospheric processes (34, 35, 33). The BRGM study used CMIP5 and CMIP6 experiments, which typically have a spatial resolution of approximately 125 km, but range from 50 to 250 km (17). The ARPEGE simulations had a spatial resolution of 14 km centered over the Atlantic Ocean (50, 51). The European Climate Risk Assessment (EUCRA) performed by the EEA used CMIP6 HighResMIP (49) for sea level rise projections around the coast and the EURO-CORDEX regional climate model (RCM) projections for essential climate variables and climate indicators over continental Europe (4, 5). Over Continental Europe, the EURO-CORDEX experiments have a spatial resolution of ~ 12 km, whereas over the other continents, the CORDEX-CORE experiments have a spatial resolution of ~ 25 km (46, 30, 31). Longueville et al. (7) mentions the potential use of regional climate model projections, within the CORDEX framework, in future studies of climate change over French Guiana. For the Guiana Space Center, CORDEX-CORE South America (30, 31), or individual studies such as Simões Reboita et al. (32), Avila-Diaz et al. (53), Dominguez et al. (37), and Bambach et al. (52) would provide the highest spatial and temporal resolution for climate projections.

Climate model projections are the basis of which the most common climate-related hazards, as well as any customized climate indices are calculated. Examples of common climate-related hazards are listed in the EU Taxonomy Climate Delegated Act, Annex I, Appendix A (104, 105). The work of Dreier et al. (71), Pfeifer et al. (72), and Nam et al. (73) show how robust statistical changes in climate indices over a small regions of interest, such as the Guiana Space Center, can be extracted, weighed, and field averaged.

3.2. *Climate Indices*

One challenge in climate services, from a data analysis perspective, is identifying and deriving tailored climate indices for a region of interest from an ensemble of projections. Research institutes which perform the climate projections have typically prioritize scientific output and invest less effort in providing model output that is usable beyond the scientific community. Herein lies the role of climate service development. Significant efforts are needed to translate the physical variables of a climate model, which include temperature, precipitation, long-wave and short-wave radiation, wind, and humidity into relevant climate information, including hazards and indices. Translating these physical variables into stakeholder relevant information, such as engineering standards or some customized index related to day-to-day operations, requires close collaboration between users or stakeholders and climate service scientists.

Climate services encompass the production of customised climate-related tools, products, and information (20). Climate service scientists employ frameworks to enhance the dialogue between stakeholders and climate scientists, helping bridge the gap between these two communities in order to transform climate data into usable and decision-relevant information (54, 20, 55, 62).

Through the dedicated process of co-development (61, 63, 64, 19), climate service scientists help identify and compute customized climate indices over the regions of interest, while documenting the limits of climate model assumptions and the uncertainties intrinsic within their projections. Climate models, which include socio-economic scenarios related to human activity, are subject to various uncertainties. These uncertainties include: model uncertainty (model design and physical parameterization schemes); initial and boundary conditions; scenario uncertainty; and internal variability of the climate system (32, 107, 57, 58, 59, 60). Climate service scientists also help overcome common technical barriers such as data volume, unfamiliar software & data formats, technical infrastructure, and scientific background knowledge, that hinder the actionable climate knowledge (62). Climate services also address the need to encompass the social dimensions of climate change such as incorporating local knowledge and values in order to build resilience (68, 21, 66, 67, 65). Awareness for climate services have been rising steadily in Europe over the last decade, but not yet operationalized.

In the public sector, customized climate indices are oftentimes developed within research and innovation projects, such as those within the EU research programmes and Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) tenders. The short-term nature of the scientific projects, however, does not guarantee that national or international institutes will take on the "operationalization" of the climate index, ultimately limiting their use by stakeholders beyond the project's lifetime. Occasionally, climate data or climate indices can have greater impacts than originally anticipated. For example, the bias corrected climate data produced within Copernicus C3S CLIM4ENERGY project (2016-2018) (111) was used to compute a health index related to the *Aedes albopictus* mosquito suitability (112), and the Universal Thermal Comfort Index software developed in the EU HORIZON2020 ANYWHERE project (EnhANCing emergencY management and response to extreme WeatHER and climate Events) (2016-2019) (108, 74) was extended to climate projections and applied to European beach tourism (73).

In the private sector, the re-/insurance sector has taken a lead in deriving climate risk indices through advancing methodologies and developing tools for communicating climate risk information (16, 117, 118, 119). They advocate for a holistic approach to climate risk assessments which should be performed across a company to ensure

consistency in both short and long-term horizons (16).

3.2.1. Exposure of the Guiana Space Center

Customized climate indices, tailored to a stakeholder's needs, will depend on a system's "operational exposure". Take for example, the Ariane 6 launch complex on the Guiana Space Center (Fig. 4). There are three areas of operation: above surface, on the surface, and below the surface. Each of these areas of operation are exposed to different climate hazards, despite being on the same site.

Figure 4. Ariane 6 launch complex processing. Credit: ESA/ArianeGroup/Arianespace/CNES. Source and copyright: European Space Agency. License: CC-BY-SA-NC-3.0-IGO. Accessed: 06.01.2024. https://www.esa.int/ESA_Multimedia/Images/2021/09/Ariane_6_launch_complex_processing

A systematic approach evaluating the different areas of operation, and the hazards relevant to them, should be performed because they may require a different type of model to address their needs. For example, to tackle concerns relating to coastal erosion or salt water intrusion a coastal hydrodynamic model or dedicated wave model is needed (82), whereas to tackle concerns about extreme wind or changing atmospheric corrosion rates a regional climate model is needed. Customized climate indices can go beyond the traditional "natural hazard" mindset (ex. heavy precipitation, wildfires, tropical storms, which are the top top 3 natural hazards requiring military deployment collected by Center for Climate and Security Military Responses to Climate Hazards Tracker (120)) and can be related to day-to-day operations. For example, at the Guiana Space Center, where corrosion is already of great concern, changes in down-welling solar radiation, atmospheric humidity, precipitation, wind speed, affect the deposition rate of chloride salts and sulfur dioxide which could become a serious problem for concrete and steel (22, 47). A study by Raposo et al. (22) mentions more research is needed to map variations of climate change on the corrosion rates of structures due to the limited number of quantitative assessments.

Once a climate index has been identified, an operational exposure assessment must be performed (23, 75). Building on the work of DeVivo et al. (75), in which a climate risk assessment framework for Mediterranean airports was performed, an exposure index was presented which considered the land-side and air-side airport facilities. The land-side facilities included offices, terminals, airports access systems and parking areas, and the air-side included runways, taxiways, tower, and aprons on the land-side DeVivo et al. (76, 77). Expanding on their original definition of climate exposure, we recommend assessing the facilities, equipment, and personnel, as well as consider the areas of operation - above-, below-, or on-the surface.

When a climate index is clearly linked to day-to-day operations, one can better assess a system's vulnerability. Climate risk vulnerability encompasses a system's sensitivity to the hazard (e.g. age of building, percentage of staff working outdoors) and its adaptive capacity (e.g. job skill set of the community, efficient drainage systems, installing nature based solutions) (75).

Climate risk assessments, using multiple customised climate indices, will help stakeholders prioritize different areas of concern, develop adaptation strategies, and manage the allocation of resources to effectively reduce risk of damage or destruction of assets and build resilience. To be truly resilient implies the system must be "able to resist, absorb, accommodate to and recover from incidents" (6). Without a comprehensive and detailed *climate* risk assessments of the Guiana Space Center, Europe is taking a reactive approach rather than a proactive approach to managing risk to European space sovereignty, civilian & economic activities, and its security.

4. Implications for European Security & Defense

From a defense perspective, the Guiana Space Center is a key component of EU space infrastructure, and urgently needs a comprehensive climate risk assessment. Admittedly, little exists in terms of publicly accessible literature to determine if climate risk assessments currently exist for the Guiana Space Center, which falls under the management of the French Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (CNES) space agency (113, 114). It is also unclear whether CNES has a dedicated office or program, similar to that of the United States of America's National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) (78), which partners *climate service scientists* with facility operators to help customize indices, though a collaboration is briefly mentioned in the French Climate and Defence Strategy report (115). Nonetheless, from a climate modelling perspective, strategically, it is essential the workflow from generating high-resolution climate projections to customized climate indices becomes operationalized, especially since climate risk assessments ought to be performed repeatedly.

Given the vast number of space threats, including kinetic anti-satellite weapons, space debris, radiation, etc., it is important that Europe can replenish its military communication, navigation, earth observation, space situational awareness, and quantum magnetometry sensity satellites (90) (Fig. 5). Furthermore, the inability to re-supply satellites, while maintaining European Space Sovereignty, has cascading effects on partnerships including centers relying on the downstream products of Copernicus Security services, such as SatCen, FRONTEx, and EMSA (116). Here we have shown climate hazards can have a direct impact on military space capabilities and strength.

In addition, strategic ground segments, including ground stations, control centers, and computing facilities ought to undergo a climate risk assessment as well to identify additional single points of failure. Anticipating climate risks and assessing vulnerabil-

(a) Threats in Space. Source and copyright: European Union (2023)

(b) Using space for security and defence. Source and copyright: European Union (2023)

Figure 5. Source and copyright: European Union (2023). License: CC-BY-4.0. Accessed: 06.01.2024. (a) Threats in Space. https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/eu-space/eu-space-strategy-security-and-defence_en (b) Using space for security and defence. https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/eu-space/eu-space-strategy-security-and-defence_en

ities for dual-use military infrastructure, such as the Guiana Space Center, requires close collaboration between defence specialists and climate scientists in order to make effective decisions regarding investments, adaptation, or even relocation (115). It will also be important to include local governance partners from French Guiana, as reliance on civilian infrastructure can compromise operational effectiveness and readiness. It would be prudent to incorporate climate hazard projections within “stress test or crisis gaming” scenarios in order to identify data bottle necks and knowledge gaps while assessing the capacity to cope, adapt, and recover.

By making climate projections operational, and incorporating climate services to co-design site-specific climate indices, decision-relevant choices can be integrated directly into day-to-day operations. These two actions would help fulfill the medium-term actions to build resilience to natural hazards and climate change in EU defence as proposed by Tavares da Costa et al. (9). Climate risks could be incorporated within the European Union’s Space Threat Response Exercises, similar to that performed in 2024 (106).

5. Relations to European policies and programmes, and Global initiatives

The importance of operational climate services is gradually being recognised at both European and international levels. This recognition is reflected in various policies aimed at managing climate risks. In this section, we outline existing French and European policies and programmes, as well as international initiatives, which could be broadened and developed upon to build resilience within Europe’s space infrastructure; ultimately safeguarding Europe’s space sovereignty.

5.1. *European policies and programmes*

Several European policies, such as the EU directive related to the assessment and management of flood risks (95), the EU directive on the resilience of critical entities (94), and EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change (93), show the necessitate the mapping of hazards and risk to the built environment and infrastructure, and planning of adaptation to the changing climate for disaster risk reduction in different EU Member States, including France and its overseas territories. As such all EU Member states have required broad risk assessments at EU and national scales.

Additionally, the European Union, through its Council Decision 2021/1764 of October 5, 2021 (92), has determined that the program associated with the Overseas Countries and Territories will allocate 25% of its total financial resources to climate objectives from 2021 to 2027.

In light of ongoing and projected climate change, European countries, as well as research agencies collecting information at the EU level, have mapped climate risks in several projects. For instance, a recent large study by the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre has focused on climate impacts and risks for Europe, looking also at strategic and economic implications (24), including broad sectors such as agriculture, electricity reduction, drought and flood risks. An earlier study looked at transport infrastructure in the EU, such as airports, seaports and inland waterways (25). These studies could be extended to critical infrastructure, in particular the Europe’s space-related infrastructure, as a potential area for further research.

In terms of available climate data for risk assessment, the Copernicus Climate Data

Store (CDS) provides easy access of climate indices for all of Europe. Currently, there are seven climate indicators (121), which include temperature, sea surface temperature, green house gas concentrations, green house gas fluxes, sea level, sea ice, ice sheets, and glaciers. The recently launched Copernicus climate atlas provides global and regional changes for different climate indices available, but are centred around traditional climate model output rather than actionable hazard or risk information (122). For the assessment of impacts and adaptation of the launching site, other information is required. It would be useful to extend to expand the Copernicus climate information to indicators that can be used for critical infrastructure risk assessment, or to engineering standards related to heat, rainfall, wind-loads and so on.

Furthermore, there is potential to expand upon the European Environmental Agency (EEA) evaluation of individual national atlases (123), which include climate projections, to include French Guiana. One can also leverage insights from the Interreg V Caribbean cooperation programme (2014-2020) (126), which primarily focused on improving the local natural hazard response capacity for improving crisis management. There is now an opportunity to focus on developing community-driven strategies to climate risk management and adaptation measures in French Guiana.

In line with the objectives of the Interreg V Caribbean cooperation programme, studies that investigate sea-level rise and extreme sea-levels related to storm surges on continental Europe's coast could be done for French Guiana (86), as well as other hazards such as waves (87), extreme heat, extreme rainfall, and drought. This would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the risks faced by the launch site and the surrounding areas.

5.2. *French policies and programmes*

In 2012, the French government, according to the requirements of the EU Floods Directive (96, 95), identified and mapped the locations in French Guiana that are vulnerable to coastal and river flood hazards. An addendum was made to this mapping in 2018 (97). These maps provide crucial information about potential hazards to the launch site, including transport to and from the sites, as well as other risks. Under the Floods Directive, these maps and consequent flood risk management plans can be expanded to include climate projections. The way climate change should be considered in these plans however is left to individual Member States. This provides an opportunity and opening to include climate services to support an assessment of flood risks under projected climate change.

In 2016, the French Guiana Territorial Collectivity approved a national decree, Décret no. 2016-931 (République Française Décret no. 2016-931), which provides actions, including establishing a space for consultation, aimed at co-constructing long-term public policies. These policies, which involve all Guyanese stakeholders, could serve as the foundation for building a local narrative on climate change adaptation.

For the Kourou launch site, it would be possible to build upon efforts done for other overseas territories, such as done for the aforementioned C3AF project in the French Antilles C3AF (109) project for which geographic and climate indices were developed. This project, funded by the European Regional Development Fund, developed indicators for hazards, exposure and vulnerabilities, for these French islands, that would be needed to do a full climate risk analysis, and assessment of options for risk reduction and adaptation.

The urgent need for enhanced climate services, as highlighted by Leroux et al. (85),

particularly for Small Island Developing States in the Southwest Indian Ocean, emphasizes the global importance of initiatives like those being undertaken by France. Climate services developed in one region can provide valuable insights and methodologies for other vulnerable regions, including French Guiana.

As of 2024, France has invested in climate modeling through the TRACCS (TRANSformer la modélisation du Climat pour les services Climatiques) program (127), jointly led by the French National Centre for Scientific Research and Météo-France, to transform climate modeling to meet societal expectations in terms of climate action. The programme aims to develop climate services co-constructed by stakeholders and climate modeling experts. One suggestion is to use the Guiana Space Center as a showcase living-lab for climate services which would benefit all Europeans. In addition, there is an opportunity to collaborate with the Observatoire Defense Climat (124), a component of IRIS (Institute for International and Strategic Relations) (125), which studies climate-related security and defence issues confronting France and its zones of strategic influence, which could include space activities.

5.3. *International initiatives*

At the international level, the Council of Strategic Risk (128) and the newly established NATO Climate Change and Security Centre of Excellence (129) will offer an opportunity to study risks related to climate, space activities, and security. This global perspective is crucial in understanding the broader implications of the climate-space-security nexus.

Building on this understanding of global climate change, initiatives like the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Destination Earth are taking a proactive approach. This initiative is developing a high-precision digital model of the Earth (89) which should provide detailed simulations of natural and human activity systems, offering stakeholders a wealth of information at an unprecedented level of detail. The Eve for Climate initiative (88) is another international effort that focuses on providing high-resolution climate information to a wide range of stakeholders, from policymakers to the general public. Both these initiatives could provide an important foundation of high resolution data for an operational climate service, including for locations outside Europe where currently such information is lacking. Linked with local data and information on exposure and vulnerability, space sector-specific climate indices could be derived from these services.

6. Conclusions

Telecommunications, navigation, and Earth observations play an important role in the day-to-day activities of Europeans. Given the importance of space-sector services, it is essential to ensure European space infrastructure is resilient to the impacts of climate change. It is widely acknowledged that the growing impacts of climate change have the potential to damage or destroy assets and infrastructure. The climatic risks impacting European space infrastructure operations, however, have not yet been quantified and published.

Climate hazards, and their projected changes in frequency, intensity, and duration, are calculated from climate model simulations. Currently, however, the production of climate projections worldwide is performed mainly at scientific research centers. As such, the understanding of future risks hinges on the foresight of scientists and of-

tentimes bound to short-term projects. This leaves critical infrastructure operators, including key European space- and security- entities, unable to reliably perform systematic climate risk assessments without active collaboration with researchers.

Critical infrastructure operators performing regular climate risk assessments would benefit from "operationalized climate services". Similar to weather forecasts, operationalized climate services would include both the periodic production of high-resolution standardized climate projections, as well as the production of customized climate indices for risk assessments. Customized climate indices can be co-developed through collaboration between sector-specialists, such as space- and security-operators, and climate service scientists. Together, through a systematic evaluation of the facilities, equipment, and personnel for different areas of operation (ex., above-, below-, on-the-surface), various climate hazards can be identified. Exposure to these hazards can be calculated. Climate service scientists can help identify which models are fit for purpose in order to develop customize climate indices relevant to the day-to-day operations of the facility.

In the case of the Guiana Space Center, a key component within Europe's space infrastructure which lies adjacent to Atlantic coast near the equatorial city of Kourou, French Guiana, examples of customized climate indices would be the changing corrosion rates calculated for facility engineers, or a thermal comfort index for personnel management. Utilizing multiple climate indices for a robust climate risk assessment is essential to accurately assess a system's vulnerability, prioritize concerns, manage resources, and ultimately devise adaptation strategies. Through climate services and the co-production process, Europe could take a proactive rather than reactive approach to managing and reducing climate risk in order to develop resilience. This is particularly important for the Guiana Space Center, where in case of damage or destruction of satellites, such as military satellites in geostationary orbit, Europe would maintain its ability launch and replenish satellites while simultaneously preserving European Space sovereignty. Without the ability to replenish satellites, all downstream services related to security, such as SatCen, FRONTEx, EMSA, and SESA are at risk. This ultimately jeopardizes the safety and security of European citizens. Therefore, climate-related hazards must be considered both a space safety- and security-risk.

We propose some recommendations to improve the safety and security of European citizens:

- (1) The European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence should consider climate hazards a safety and security risk;
- (2) The production of climate projections and derivation of customized climate indices should be standardized and performed regularly;
- (3) Co-development of climate indices for critical infrastructure operators and climate service scientists should evaluate the facilities, equipment, and personnel for different areas of operation (ex., above-, below-, on-the-surface) to assess potential hazards;
- (4) For each climate hazard identified, a climate risk assessment should be performed.

We have also identified relevant existing policies, programmes, and initiatives in France, the EU, and globally, which could be built upon in order to: (i) develop and support local capacities; (ii) develop and evaluate different risk reduction options and adaptation strategies; and (iii) ultimately improve the provision of local- and site-specific information to assess projected climate hazards and risks for the European space infrastructure.

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Authors contribution

C.N. conceived and designed the study, L.B. secured funding, and all authors contributed to the writing and editing of the final manuscript and approved its submission for publication.

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*Safeguarding European space sovereignty - Recommendations for
Operational Climate Services*

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